

Insomnia as a Predictor of Depression and Anxiety Disorders: A Narrative Review

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Abstract

Introduction: Insomnia, one of the most prevalent sleep disorders, is strongly associated with depression and anxiety [1,2]. Increasing longitudinal evidence suggests that insomnia may not only co-occur with affective and anxiety symptoms, but also precede and predict their onset. Early identification and both pharmacological and non-pharmacological interventions, particularly cognitive behavioral therapy for insomnia (CBT-I), may reduce the risk of developing depression and have important clinical implications [1,3,4].

Purpose: This study summarizes open-access evidence on insomnia as a predictor of depression and anxiety disorders, with particular attention to longitudinal studies, potential mediating mechanisms, and clinical implications, including preventive interventions targeting insomnia.

Methods: This narrative review was based on open-access, peer-reviewed literature identified through databases such as PubMed Central and other open-access journals. Particular emphasis was placed on prospective cohort studies and meta-analyses investigating temporal associations between baseline insomnia and subsequent depression or anxiety [1,5]; studies examining bidirectional relationships and potential mediating mechanisms [6]; and randomized controlled trials (RCTs) assessing the effects of cognitive behavioral therapy for insomnia (CBT-I), including digital and app-based interventions, on subsequent mental health outcomes [3].

Results: Prospective evidence indicates that insomnia and restless sleep increase the risk of anxiety, which may precedes the development of depression [1,11]. Evidence suggests that treating insomnia especially with cognitive behavioral therapy for insomnia (CBT-I), including digital/app-based formats, can reduce depressive symptoms and may help prevent major depressive disorder in high-risk youth [3] and reduce depression risk in adults [12].

Conclusion: Insomnia appears to be a clinically meaningful, potentially modifiable predictor of both depression and anxiety. Incorporating systematic insomnia assessment and evidence-based insomnia treatment (CBT-I, including scalable digital approaches) may contribute to prevention strategies and improve mental health trajectories.

Keywords:

insomnia; depressive disorders; anxiety disorders; cognitive behavioral therapy insomnia; insomnia and depression

Introduction

Insomnia is a highly prevalent sleep disorder characterized by persistent difficulties initiating sleep, maintaining sleep, or experiencing early morning awakenings with inability to return to sleep. Mounting evidence indicates that insomnia may precede the onset of major mental disorders, including depression and anxiety. From a clinical perspective, if insomnia reliably predicts subsequent psychopathology, it becomes a strategic target for early identification, risk stratification, and preventive interventions. Moreover, individuals receiving treatment for sleep disturbances should also be carefully assessed for the presence of anxiety and depressive disorders.

A meta-analysis of prospective cohort studies indicates that insomnia is associated with an increased risk of developing depression over follow-up periods. The associations differed across ethnic groups, with the meta-analytic findings demonstrating a greater risk increase in U.S. samples relative to European populations [1]. Classic longitudinal research also suggests chronic insomnia increases the risk of both anxiety and depression [5]. These findings align with clinical observations that persistent sleep disturbance often predates full syndrome presentations of depression and anxiety.

At the same time, bidirectional relationships between sleep and depression or anxiety disorders have been founded in longitudinal studies. Both anxiety and depression were associated with an increased risk of subsequent insomnia, while insomnia was associated with elevated levels of future anxiety and depression [6]. Symptoms of depression and anxiety can worsen sleep via rumination, worry, autonomic arousal, and behavioral changes; conversely, poor sleep can amplify emotional reactivity, impair coping, and reduce cognitive control. In children and adolescents, longitudinal work suggests sleep problems both predict and are predicted by a cluster of disorders including depression, generalized anxiety and oppositional defiant disorder [7]. The systematic review additionally confirms bidirectional

relationships between sleep disturbances, anxiety, and depression, indicating mutually reinforcing effects over time [8]. In this context, insomnia can be understood not only as an early warning sign but also as a mechanism sustaining symptom escalation.

The public health relevance is substantial. Insomnia is common, often undertreated, and potentially modifiable. Treating insomnia may reduce the risk of developing anxiety and depressive disorders, and conversely, effective treatment of these disorders may improve sleep outcomes [8]. This possibility is supported by randomized controlled trials (RCTs) of CBT-I and app-based cognitive behavioral therapy for insomnia (CBT-I) interventions showing improvements in sleep and downstream mental health outcomes. Digital Cognitive Behavioral Therapy for Insomnia (CBT-I) prevents the onset of major depressive disorder and improves sleep outcomes in youth with insomnia and subclinical depressive symptoms [3,12]. These advances support a preventive framework: treat insomnia early, reduce later depression or anxiety disorders.

This narrative review synthesizes open-access literature on insomnia as a predictor of depression and anxiety disorders, explores plausible mechanisms and bidirectional pathways, and discusses clinical implications, including evidence for CBT-I and digital interventions as scalable preventive tools.

Aim of the Review

This review aims to synthesize evidence on insomnia as a predictor of depression and anxiety, examine bidirectional and mediating mechanisms, and highlight clinical and preventive implications, with a focus on CBT-I, including digital interventions.

Methods

This narrative review draws on open-access publications focused primarily on: prospective cohort studies and meta-analyses examining temporal associations between baseline insomnia and subsequent depression or anxiety; studies investigating bidirectional relationships using longitudinal reciprocal models; research exploring mediation pathways (e.g., insomnia as a mediator between anxiety and later depression); and randomized controlled trials evaluating cognitive behavioral therapy for insomnia (CBT-I), particularly digital or app-based interventions, with mental health outcomes as endpoints.

Discussion

Insomnia as a Predictor of Depression

Meta-analysis of prospective cohort studies found that insomnia is associated with a higher risk of incident depression across follow-up intervals. The study incorporated data from thirty-four prospective cohort studies minimizing the likelihood that the findings reflect isolated, sample-specific effects. Statistical analysis demonstrated that insomnia significantly increased the risk of subsequent depression [1]. Importantly, by establishing temporal direction, the prospective data suggest that insomnia frequently predates depressive episodes.

The study from the Wisconsin Sleep Cohort Study investigated whether insomnia predicts the longitudinal onset of depression rather than simply co-occurring with it. A sample of 555 adult participants without baseline depression was followed for approximately four years. Both self-reported insomnia symptoms and objective polysomnographic markers of disturbed sleep significantly increased

the risk of developing depression, with risk estimates ranging from approximately 2.2- to 5.3-fold [9]. This is notable because it suggests that the risk of subsequent depression related to insomnia is not just a matter of self-report or perception, but is reflected in measurable tests.

Data showed that even mild insomnia may increase the risk of subsequently developing depression. The likelihood of developing depression increased with higher baseline insomnia severity. Even after accounting for occupational status, cohabitation status, sleep duration, current treatment or medication use, insomnia continued to independently predict the onset of depression. It may be important to assess insomnia severity using validated instruments, such as the Athens Insomnia Scale (AIS), to facilitate early detection and preventive intervention [10].

Although insomnia has been identified as a predictor of depression, some longitudinal research increasingly reveals a dynamic and reciprocal relationship between these conditions. During the first year of the COVID-19 pandemic in Ireland, analyses showed that insomnia symptoms predicted later depressive symptoms, and depressive symptoms predicted later insomnia symptoms, indicating bidirectionality [11]. These findings point to a mutually reinforcing process in which sleep disturbances and depressive symptoms intensify one another over time. Clinically, this reinforces the argument for early insomnia intervention: if insomnia contributes to symptom escalation and becomes reciprocally reinforced, treating insomnia early may help prevent or attenuate the reciprocal escalation of depressive symptoms.

Treating Insomnia to Reduce Depression Risk

Targeting insomnia as a modifiable risk factor for depression may yield meaningful mental health benefits. In youth with insomnia and subclinical depression, app-based CBT-I was effective in preventing subsequent major depressive disorder and reducing nocturnal and daytime impairments among high-risk individuals [3]. This is particularly compelling because it demonstrates the potential of digital interventions to improve mental health outcomes in youth populations

In adults, a randomized trial demonstrated that digital CBT-I could contribute to depression prevention, with benefits maintained during follow-up. It is not only an effective treatment for comorbid insomnia and depression, but also a highly effective intervention for the prevention of depressive disorders [12].

Insomnia as a Predictor of Anxiety Disorders

Insomnia is also linked to anxiety disorders, particularly to generalized anxiety processes. Evidence indicates that chronic insomnia predicts later anxiety and depression [5]. During childhood and adolescence, sleep disturbances frequently co-occur with various psychiatric disorders including anxiety disorders, oppositional defiant disorder and depression [7]. Longitudinal syntheses indicate that insomnia and poor sleep quality are reciprocally associated with anxiety and depression. However, in childhood populations, sleep problems significantly predicted subsequent increases in depressive symptoms and in a combined depression–anxiety outcome, whereas the reverse relationship was not observed [8]. These findings highlight the importance of screening young individuals for sleep problems, as such disturbances may serve both as early indicators of psychological vulnerability and as symptoms shaped by emerging psychopathology.

Insomnia as a Bridge Between Anxiety and Depression

A clinically and theoretically important issue is comorbidity: anxiety and depression frequently co-occur, and one condition may increase the risk of the other. Study showed how insomnia mediated the longitudinal relationship between anxiety in adolescence and later depression in adulthood and helps explain how anxiety symptoms translate into later depressive symptoms. Worry and catastrophic thinking, which are common in anxiety disorders, may contribute to sleep problems, particularly difficulties falling asleep. Poor sleep may adversely affect cognitive functioning, including attention, impulse control, and memory. Insomnia in anxious individuals may strengthen the focus on negative memories, thereby contributing to a greater risk of depressive symptoms [14]. From a clinical perspective, this suggested that treating insomnia in individuals with anxious disorders may reduce the likelihood of subsequent depressive escalation. It also aligns with the observation that anxious arousal such as excessive worry and hypervigilance, can impair sleep onset and maintenance, and that persistent sleep disruption may contribute to emotional exhaustion, reduced positive affect, and the development of depressive symptoms.

Persistence of Insomnia Under Stress and Implications for Anxiety Trajectories

During the 12 months of the COVID-19 pandemic as a period characterized by high stress, authors examined the relationship between insomnia and stressful circumstances. A longitudinal cohort study found that insomnia was more likely to persist than remit following periods of stress and uncertainty, and that factors such as sleep reactivity and sleep effort predicted trajectories [15]. These findings underscore the importance of monitoring sleep problems after stressful events, as early identification and intervention may help prevent the subsequent development of depression and anxiety. Early intervention may be particularly beneficial during stress transitions like adolescence, occupational stress, family caregiving.

Mechanisms Linking Insomnia with Depression and Anxiety

A systematic review focusing on insomnia and anxiety-related disorders emphasized the complex link between insomnia and anxiety symptomatology. Potential mechanisms highlight the central role of insomnia-related hyperarousal and dysfunctional cognitive processes, which can promote maladaptive stress responses, impair emotion regulation, and reinforce the cycle of worry characteristic of anxiety [16]. This work supports conceptualizing insomnia as a legitimate target in anxiety care, not simply as a secondary symptom. Importantly, insomnia-focused interventions may complement anxiety-focused CBT.

Evidence highlights that changes in insomnia status matter. In a longitudinal study, changes in insomnia predicted the incidence and persistence of anxiety and depression: incident insomnia increased risk for new-onset anxiety and depression as well as maintenance of depression [17]. Insomnia may represent a dynamic risk factor that emerges in response to life changes and subsequently increases vulnerability to mental health disorders.

This insight is important for prevention: monitoring sleep changes may allow earlier detection of risk trajectories, enabling timely interventions that could prevent the development of full disorders.

Young adulthood is a high-risk period for the onset of depression and anxiety, and sleep problems are common due to irregular schedules, academic demands, and psychosocial stressors. A prospective cohort study found that sleep features predicted subsequent mental disorders with the strongest

associations observed between sleep problems and the prevalence of major depressive episodes and generalized anxiety disorder. Data showed insomnia as a risk marker in young adults [18]. Additionally, research among university students identified psychological predictors of insomnia (perfectionism, low self-esteem and external locus of control) and showed that insomnia may forecast later anxiety and depressive symptoms, suggesting potential prevention targets within student mental health programs [19]. These findings highlight the value of early screening and sleep-focused interventions in young people.

Clinical Implications: Assessment, Treatment, and Prevention

Clinical practice guidelines emphasize behavioral and psychological treatments (including CBT-I) as effective interventions for chronic insomnia [20]. If insomnia predicts depression and anxiety, CBT-I can be framed not only as a sleep treatment but also as a proactive approach to reducing mental health risks. This perspective encourages early insomnia treatment in primary care and routine sleep assessment.

Digital CBT-I (dCBT-I) expands access for patients by reducing barriers related to therapist availability, cost, and it can be a first step of starting the therapy. A systematic review and meta-analysis found internet-delivered CBT-I is effective in improving sleep in adults with insomnia [21]. Such evidence supports the feasibility of delivering insomnia interventions at scale, which is crucial if the goal includes prevention of widespread mental health burden.

A nationwide decentralized RCT demonstrated the effectiveness of a fully automated digital CBT-I program in U.S. adults. The study showed that digital CBT-I may be cost-effective relative to other treatments [13]. In older adults, a digital CBT-I RCT also demonstrated clinically meaningful benefits in sleep and functioning [22], supporting effectiveness across age groups.

Some commonly used pharmacological and non-pharmacological interventions, particularly cognitive behavioral therapy for insomnia, have demonstrated efficacy and acceptable risk–benefit profiles. Therefore, evidence-based, systematic assessment and treatment of insomnia should be prioritized in clinical practice [23]. From an implementation standpoint, these insights support routine insomnia screening in patients presenting with anxiety or depressive symptoms and, importantly, screening for anxiety/depression in patients presenting with insomnia. Doing so may improve early detection and enable targeted interventions—especially CBT-I.

Limitations of the Evidence

Despite robust associations, several limitations should be considered:

1. **Heterogeneous insomnia definitions** across studies (different scales, thresholds, and diagnostic criteria) can affect estimated risk magnitude.
2. **Self-report bias** remains common in sleep measurement, though cohorts like the Wisconsin study strengthen inference by incorporating more detailed sleep markers [9].
3. **Confounding factors** (stress, substance use, medical comorbidity, circadian rhythm issues) can contribute to both insomnia and mental health symptoms.
4. **Bidirectionality** complicates causal inference; insomnia can predict depression/anxiety, but emotional symptoms can also worsen sleep [7,8,11].

5. **Generalizability** of RCT findings depends on adherence, engagement, and implementation context, especially in digital interventions [13,21].

Nonetheless, converging evidence from prospective cohorts, mediation analyses, and RCTs supports the clinical importance of insomnia as both a marker and a potentially modifiable risk factor.

Conclusions

Open-access evidence indicates that insomnia is a meaningful predictor of later depression and anxiety, with substantial support from prospective cohort studies and meta-analytic synthesis [1,5]. Developmental research shows reciprocal associations between sleep problems and anxiety–depression clusters, suggesting transactional processes over time [7,8]. A study indicates insomnia can mediate the pathway from anxiety to later depression, highlighting a plausible mechanism for comorbidity progression [14]. Intervention studies suggest that treating insomnia, especially with CBT-I and digital/app-based formats, can reduce depressive symptoms and may prevent major depression in high-risk populations [3,12]. Clinical guidelines endorse behavioral treatments as first-line insomnia care [20], and broader clinical reviews emphasize the importance of integrating insomnia management into routine practice [23].

Overall, insomnia should be treated as a core clinical target in mental health prevention strategies. Systematic insomnia screening and early access to CBT-I, potentially via digital platforms, may help reduce the incidence, persistence, and severity of depression and anxiety disorders.

Disclosure

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